

A novel approach for sizing and optimization of hybrid solar-PV, biogas-generator, and batteries system for rural electrification: case study

Cheibany Cheikh Ebeya¹, Mohamed Mahmoud Ali¹, Mamoudou Ndongo¹, Ahmed Sidibba²,
Kaan Yetilmmezsoy³, Emel Kiyas³, Boudy Bilal⁴, Eslemhoum Jedou¹, Halima Maiguizo Diagne⁵,
Issakha Youm⁵

¹Department of Physics, University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya (UNA), Nouakchott, Mauritania

²Department of Exact Sciences, Higher Normal School of Nouakchott, Mauritania

³Department of Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul, Turkey

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ecole Supérieure Polytechnique (ESP), Nouakchott, Mauritania

⁵Center of Studies and Research on Renewable Energies (CERER), University Cheikh Anta Diop of Dakar (UCAD), Senegal

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ABSTRACT

A new approach for sizing a hybrid solar-PV-battery and biogas generator for power generation was suggested in this study, based on the variation of energy resources and the load profile. Biogas has enormous potential and numerous economic and social advantages. In this respect, the monthly solar radiation, temperature, and biogas produced from biomass resources were used as model inputs. This study considers the total annualized of the components for the feasibility analysis. HOMER Pro[®] software-based outcomes in the proposed methodology revealed that the proposed solar biogas hybrid system was sufficient to meet the load requirements of the village (Ain Farba village in the Hodh El Gharbi area located in the northeast of the Mauritania country) with a net present cost over the 25-year lifespan of 61,144 \$ and the energy cost was determined to be 0.0473 \$/kWh.

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Corresponding Author:

Cheibany Cheikh Ebeya
Department of Physics, University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya (UNA)
Nouakchott 880, Mauritania
Email: cheibanycheikh6@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Population growth, rising living standards, mobility, and globalization dynamics have all contributed to rapid increase in energy demand in recent years [1]. As a result, about 15% of the world's population lacks access to electricity [2], [3]. Further, approximately 600 million people in Africa do not have access to electricity. Problems with limited fossil fuel reserves and the negative consequences of traditional energy sources that contribute to global warming, as well as the negative consequences of traditional energy sources, have prompted the search for more sustainable energy technologies [4], [5]. As a result, renewable power technologies such as solar, wind, hydro, bioenergy, and their hybridization have become common electricity generation alternatives [6], [7]. Therefore, it is interesting to take into account hydrogen positioned as the accelerator of the energy transition.

The rate of access to electrification in Mauritania was around 45% in 2019 [8]. In fact, Mauritania has significant renewable energy sources that include wind [9], solar [10], biomass [11], and even small-scale hydroelectricity [12]. Further, Mauritania was one of the first countries in Sub-Saharan Africa to have installed large renewable energy projects, including 15 MW and 50 MW solar PV power plant in two different locations,

in Nouakchott, 4.4 MW solar PV plant installed by National Industrial and Mining Company of Mauritania (SNIM), 30 MW wind farm in Nouakchott [13], and 100 MW wind power plant in progress at Boulanoir. Stand-alone and mini-grid systems are currently viewed as among the most cost-effective alternative energy options required to expand and accelerate access to electricity in many rural communities [14]. Further, in remote areas, combining renewable energy sources (photovoltaic, wind, and biomass) with conventional energy sources (internal combustion engines) or hybrid installations is a more cost-effective option than grid connection [15], [16]. In addition, supplying electricity to remote areas mostly through grid extension can be costly and frequently necessitates long-term planning [17]. Renewable energy can also benefit villages with unreliable power grids due to frequent blackouts, particularly during peak hours or in off-grid areas [18]. The hybrid system is primarily intended to generate electricity from renewable energy sources, while the traditional source, which serves as an auxiliary source, is the best compromise capable of producing enough energy to meet the needs of small villages and rural areas [19].

Several studies on hybrid renewable energy systems for rural electrification, in remote and isolated communities have been conducted. For example, Odoi *et al.* [20] investigated the use of a hybrid solar PV/biogas/battery power system to provide electricity to remote communities in Ghana. They used the HOMER software to model and investigate the hybrid energy system's technical, economic, and environmental aspects. They found that the PV/biogas/battery hybrid system outperformed the PV/diesel/battery and diesel systems. In a different study, Podder *et al.* [21] proposed an energy-based method for charging electric vehicles (EVs) using solar photovoltaic (PV) and biogas as two sustainable energy sources. They employed HOMER software to examine the power generated while considering solar photovoltaic and biogas charging stations for electric vehicles. Since the NPC and COE were 93,530 \$ and 0.181 \$/kWh, respectively, they decided on a 4.5 kW solar PV installation. Further, the authors described a method to design the best hybrid diesel/PV/wind/battery (HRES) for the electrification of residential structures in rural areas [22]. A standard geographic information system program (ArcGIS 10.2) was used in this study to create a map of Algeria's potential for renewable energy. In addition, a constraint approach and a particle swarm optimization algorithm were used to address the multi-objective design of the hybrid renewable energy system. According to this study, the optimal design for Adrar and Tindouf was determined to be PV/wind/diesel/battery, while the best configuration for the other locations was determined to be PV/diesel/battery. Murugaperumal *et al.* [23] presented a hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) with an optimal design and technical-economic feasibility for applications involving rural electrification. By using Homer software, multiple approaches were used to determine the best hybrid renewable energy (HRE) configurations for optimum performance, and it was determined that the company's suggested efficient strategy. In a different inquiry, Teferra [24] presented a study of the potential for renewable energy applications, feasibility analysis of the hybrid PV generator using biogas and biodiesel, and a comparison of the obtained solutions to the existing networks to feed a rural community. Kumar and Saini [25] investigated an integrated, grid-independent hybrid renewable energy system to provide electricity and fresh water to a numerous of unconnected villages in the Indian state of Odisha. In another study, Baruah *et al.* [26] provides a technical and economic feasibility of a standalone hybrid renewable energy system for generating power to meet the needs of an Indian university. Solar radiation, wind speed, biogas, syngas, and hydrokinetic power were the resources taken into account for this study. HOMER Pro® software was used for the feasibility study. Based on the net present cost (NPC), levelized cost of energy (LCOE), battery storage, emissions, space needs, and employment potential, 31 distinct alternative combinations of the various technologies were examined. The analytical hierarchy process (AHP), a well-known method for multi-criteria decision support, was used to find the best combination. With an NPC of 5 million dollars and a COE of 0.095 \$/kWh, the hybrid PV-wind-biogas-syngas-hydrokinetic-battery renewable energy system was the best configuration. In the [27], [28], the authors evaluated the feasibility of three different systems (a non-renewable system, a stand-alone renewable system, and a hybrid renewable system) to provide energy to a rural hamlet in Borneo, Malaysia. They discovered that the hybrid PV/diesel/batteries system, the stand-alone PV system, the hybrid PV/hydrokinetic system, and the non-renewable system all had the lowest NPC. Significantly, it was possible to power the isolated communities in Malaysian Borneo using renewable energy sources (photovoltaic/hydrokinetic). Another Italian study [29] examined the best system layout for three remote area without grid access in different climate zones of Peru: Campo Serio, El Potrero, and Silicucho. The analysis took into account seven different configurations, including single-component (solar, wind, and diesel) and hybrid systems. The HOMER software was used to determine the best system configuration. The hybrid solar-wind-diesel system was the most economically viable option for all of the communities studied. The authors in the study [30] developed an optimization approach for the feasibility study of a hybrid renewable energy system, as well as to determine the optimal size of different renewable energy technologies and to assist decision-makers in their performance survey. To solve the multi-objective optimization problem, a simulation-based optimization method combined with a constraint technique was developed. The developed algorithm's performance was evaluated and validated using the HOMER software. Oladigbolu *et al.* [31] used HOMER software to investigate the technical-economic feasibility and optimization of a micro-hydro hybrid photovoltaic-diesel-battery-wind system designed to power a typical remote village in southern Nigeria. According to the

results of the experiments and benchmark tests, the hybrid water/PV/wind/diesel/battery system was the most appealing option for off-grid rural electrification. According to the study, the optimal system had an NPC and COE of 1.01 million \$ and 0.106 \$/kWh, respectively, with a renewable energy rate of 77.4% and an environmental pollutant emission of 228,945 kg/year. Furthermore, Odou *et al.* [32] presented a technical-economic feasibility study of a hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) for long-term rural electrification in Benin. The hybrid PV/diesel generator/battery was determined to be the best configuration with the lowest NPC. Abaye and Haro [33] also used the Homer to carry out study on the evaluation of the energy resource potential and the feasibility of a hybrid PV-wind-biogas system with backup battery storage. They found that the best configuration for supplying the village includes the renewable energy technologies. Further, Ronad and Jangamshetti [34] performed the optimal cost of a wind-PV hybrid system connected to DC and AC irrigation pumps. The authors concludes that the annual electricity production of the two systems was nearly equal. However, the comparison between the costs of AC and DC loads showed that AC pumps could lead to uneconomical results and overproduction for small irrigation systems powered by renewable energy, while the DC pumps were proven more economical and reliable.

The above literature reveals that a lot of works have been reported around the world on improving the uses of the renewable energy. However, although 65% of Mauritians do not have access to electricity and the country has significant potential for solar energy and biogas, very little work has been done in Mauritania on the electrification of rural areas far from the grid using a hybrid PV-biogas system. Considering this apparent literature gap, in the present study, it was aimed to develop a novel approach for sizing and optimization of a hybrid renewable energy system solar-PV, batteries, generator biogas for the electrification of rural areas valorizing the animal manure through. Furthermore, the feasibility of a hybrid power plant PV/biogas/batteries was studied for the case of Ain Farba in Mauritania based on the proposed methodology.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the sources of the energy used for sizing the hybrid system. Section 3 presents the concept of the hybrid PV-batteries-biogas system for the decentralized application. Moreover, section 4 presents the modeling of the different device of this system and discusses the results. Finally, section 5 concludes the present study.

2. METHOD

2.1. Solar energy source

The location of this study is El Medina shown in Figure 1, located at 15°45.2' north latitude and 10° 18.1' east longitude, in the commune of Ain Farba (Hodh el Gharbi) in the northeast from Mauritania. For this study, HOMER Pro® was used to calculate global horizontal solar radiation through coordinates. According to data obtained from the NASA Surface Weather and Solar Energy website, the annual average solar radiation (SR) at El Medina Village was approximately 5.82 kWh/m²/day. Figure 2 illustrates the monthly average of the global horizontal solar radiation of the village El Medina, Location: WJQ4+VC Ain Farba (H, Mauritania) (15°56.4'N, 10°23.6'W). The highest solar radiation (SR > to 6 kWh/m²/day) is observed for the period from March to July (dry season). The lowest is observed for the December with SR=4.5 kWh/m²/day. The all cleared index is between 0.5 and 0.60, that means the site is located in region which correspond to the moderate sky.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the site

Figure 2. Monthly variation of the solar radiation and clarity index of the site

2.1. Biomass sources

The raw material needed for the formation of biogas was the manure of live animals in the village of El-Medina. The village contains 100 families each owning about 120-160 sheep and goats, 40-50 cows, 1-2 camels, 2-3 horses, and 3-4 donkeys. This study assumes that the animals of this village are distributed as follows: 47 large ruminants (cows, donkeys, camels, and horses) and 120 small ruminants (sheep and goats). This distribution gives a potential of 1.25 tons of animal waste/day. This assumption was used as one of the constraints of the HOMER Pro® model. The percentage of CH₄ in this study was assumed to be 60% [34], [35]. In addition, the daily quantity of waste according to the type of animal in Mauritania according to 2016 data [36] is given in Table 1, and the range of biogas production according to livestock waste and solid content corresponding totals (TS) is presented in Table 2 [36], [37]. On the other hand, 1 m³ of CH₄ corresponds to 36 MJ, corresponding to equal to 10 kWh [37], [38]. Figure 3 presents the biomass resources used for our study.

Table 1. Quantity of live animal manure for different ruminants

Live animal	Weight of the body (kg)	Manure (kg/day)	Blood (kg/day)	Rumen (kg/day)
Ruminants of great size	250	22.5	21	30
Poultry small ruminants	40	1.6	1.2	10
Poultry small ruminants	1.5	0.045	0.03	0.3

Table 2. Range of biogas production according to livestock waste and corresponding total solids (TS) content [38], [39]

Livestock waste	TS (%)	Biogas (m ³ * kg ⁻¹ * TS)
Camels	30 – 45	0.3 – 0.4
Cows	25 – 30	0.6 – 0.8
Goats and Sheep	18 – 25	0.3 – 0.4
Poultry	10 – 29	0.3 – 0.8
Blood	18	0.3 – 0.6
Rumen	12 – 16	0.3 – 0.6

Figure 3. Monthly variation of the biomass resource

2.2. Location of the site

Ain Farba is one of the eight municipalities of the department of Tintane, located in the region of Hodh El Gharbi in Mauritania. At the 2000 census, it had a population of 7,677 and included several villages such as El Medina located at 5 km north of Ain Farba city center. The village consists of 100 families of 4-5 people. In addition, there are a two-room (1st and 2nd grade) elementary school and a mosque in the village.

Currently, this village does not have access to electricity, and the only solution is to install an autonomous system because the center of Ain Farba municipality has only one generator, which does not meet the needs of the center, and it is economically feasible to connect to the national grid.

2.3. Demand load profile

The village consists of 100 families, a school and a mosque. The daily electrical load profile is estimated based on basic service demands such as lighting, communications, and other appliances. The total electricity village consumption is 402.28 kWh/day with the maximum power of 57.1 kW per day. The estimated daily load profile for the village is displayed in Table 3, and Figure 4 illustrates the load profile.

Table 3. Daily energy demand for the village

Village	Devices	Unity	Watt	Operating hour (h)	Total energy demand per 100 families (kWh/d)
100 families	lamp	4	40	8	128
	Fan	2	60	9	108
	TV	1	100	6	60
	portable	4	2	8	6.4
	Pump	4	4,776	4	76,416
					378,816
School	Lamp	4	40	6	0.96
	Fan	2	60	9	1.08
	PC	1	200	4	0.8
	portable	2	2	6	0.024
	Pump	1	4,776	2	9,552
					12,414
Mosque	Lampe	2	40	6	0.96
	Fan	1	60	9	0.54
	Pump	1	4,776	2	9,552
					402.28

Figure 4. Daily electrical load profile

3. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

Photovoltaic panels, a biogas engine generator, a converter, and storage batteries are all part of the proposed power system. As shown in Figure 5, the PV panels and battery system are connected to the DC bus, while the biogas generator is connected to the AC bus. The communication between the two buses is served by a bi-directional converter.

Figure 5. Block diagram of the hybrid PV-BioGasG-Batteries system

3.1. Solar PV system

To determine the power generated by a photovoltaic solar panel, it is necessary to determine the meteorological parameters such as solar radiation shown in Figure 2, cell temperature, monthly average temperature and wind speed. The expected energy output of the system is expressed in (1) [40].

$$E(t)_{pv} = R(t) * \eta_{pv} * S \quad (1)$$

Where $R(t)$ is the hourly solar radiation in W/m^2 , η_{pv} is the yield of the PV panel, and S is the area of the PV modules.

In Mauritania, the cost per watt of photovoltaic panels manufactured about 1 \$/watt while the cost per watt of panels manufactured in China is about 0,28 \$/watt, with a power greater than 220 W [41]. The characteristics of the solar panels chosen and the different types of costs are presented in the Table 4, and the photovoltaic production is given by [40], [41].

$$P_p = P_{pn} * f_d * \left(\frac{I_s}{S_I}\right) * \left(1 + \alpha_c * (T_p - T_{pn})\right) \quad (2)$$

Where P_p is the PV power-output (W), P_{pn} is the nominal power under standard PV conditions (kW), f_d is the PV derating factor (%), I_s is the incident solar radiation on a horizontal plane (W/m^2), S_I is the maximum solar radiation ($1000 W/m^2$), α_c is the thermal power coefficient ($%/^{\circ}C$), T_p is the temperature of the operation PV cell ($^{\circ}C$) at the current time step, and T_{pn} is the nominal operating cell temperature of the PV cell under standard test conditions (at $25^{\circ}C$).

Table 4. Characteristics and cost of a solar panel

Description	Value/explanation
Monitoring system	Fixed
Nominal operating temperature of the cell	47 $^{\circ}C$
The coefficient of temperature	0.4%/ $^{\circ}C$
Efficiency under standard test conditions	18% [42],[43]
Derating factor	80%
Capital cost of operation and maintenance	640 \$/kw
Replacement cost	640 \$/kW
Lifetime	25 years

3.2. Battery

In this study, the main source of energy was the biogas/solar PV generators. An additional storage system was proposed to store the excess energy from the renewable sources. A charge control system was used to prevent overcharging and deep discharging of the batteries. The nominal capacity of the battery is given in (4) [42], [43].

$$E_b = \frac{E_d * d_a}{\eta_i * \eta_b * b_d} \quad (3)$$

Where E_d is the total energy demand, d_a is the day number of the autonomy, b_d is the depth of discharge of the battery, η_i is the efficiency of the inverter, and η_b is the efficiency of the battery. The characteristics and costs of the battery are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Characteristics of the studied battery

Battery	Iron Edison Nickel Iron	References
Nominal capacity	200 Amp-Hours (Ah) (0.24 kWh)	[44]
Nominal voltage	1.2 V	
Nominal capital cost of operation and maintenance	130 \$	
Replacement cost	100 \$	
Lifetime	5.57	

3.3. Converter

A converter containing an inverter-rectifier system was intended to connect the DC bus to the AC bus. The characteristics and costs of the selected converter are given in Table 6, and the energy of the system output is given by the following expressions [44]:

$$E_{in}(t) = \eta_c * E_{bi}(t) \quad (4)$$

$$E_{ou}(t) = \eta_r * E_{bi}(t) \quad (5)$$

where $E_{in}(t)$ and $E_{ou}(t)$ are the hourly energies at the input and output of the inverter respectively, η_r and η_c are the rectifier and inverter efficiencies respectively, $E_{bi}(t)$ is the hourly energy of the battery to supply the load, and $E_{bi}(t)$, the hourly value of the energy surplus of the biogas generator.

Table 6. Characteristics and costs of the chosen converter

Description	Value /explanation	References
Efficiency	90%	[44], [45]
Cost of capital	550\$/Kw	
Capital and replacement cost	450 \$/kW	
Cost of operating	5 \$/kW/year	
Lifetime	15 years	

3.4. Biogas generator

Assuming the same amount of water (1370 liters), the potential waste available (mainly manure) was estimated as 1.25 tons/day. Therefore, the digester required a capacity of 2.74 m³/day of substrate. It is noted that this potential can ensure a continuous supply of biogas to meet the electricity needs of the village. The costs of digesters and biogas generators are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Costs of the digester

Nominal capacity	6 kW	References
Yield	95%	[45], [46]
Investment and replacement cost	742 \$/kW	
Operation and maintenance cost	0.015 \$/kWh	
Lifetime	20 years	

The electrical energy generated from biogas is given by (6) [46].

$$e_{bio} = E_{bio} * \eta_{be} \quad (6)$$

Where e_{bio} is the amount of electricity produced, E_{bio} is the raw unconverted energy of biogas and η_{be} indicates demonstrates the general effectiveness conversion of biogas into energy.

3.5. Economic parameters

The interest rate and the project's lifetime are the economic model's input parameters. In this study, the interest rate and lifetime were assumed to be equal to 10% and 20 years, respectively. The NPC and cost of energy (COE) are given by (7) and (10) [46]:

$$NPC = \frac{C_{ann,total}}{CRF(i,n)} \quad (7)$$

CRF is the capital recovery factor, it is given by the following equation:

$$CRF(i, n) = \frac{i*(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (8)$$

where $C_{ann,total}$ is the total annualized cost, n is the interest rate, and i is the lifetime of the project in years.

$$i = \frac{i' - f}{1 + f} \quad (9)$$

where i is the nominal interest rate is i' , and f is the annual inflation rate. The value of the energy cost is computed by the (10):

$$COE = \frac{C_{ann,total}}{E_{served}} \quad (10)$$

where E_{served} is the total electric load served by the system.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the obtained results from the model are presented in following. In the first part, the optimization results are described, then the comparison with the electricity network and other international networks is analyzed.

4.1. Optimization results

The input parameters defined for each component in the system component specification section were used with HOMER Pro[®] to analyze the feasibility of the PV-BiogasG-Batteries system necessary to meet the electrical load. The six viable configurations optimized based on increasing the net present cost (NPC) are given in the Table 8. It should be noted that the best configuration is the one corresponding to the lowest NPC value [47]. In addition, this system configuration consisted of a 20 kW biogas engine, a 15 kW photovoltaic generator, 44 batteries, capacity 200 Ah/battery, and nominal voltage 12 V and an inverter with nominal capacity of 10 kW. Moreover, it corresponded to an initial capital of 26,126 \$, operating cost of 3,858 \$/year, NPC of 61,144 \$, and a COE of 0.0473 \$/kWh. These results are similar to those in the [48]. The initial capital costs, replacement cost, and the operating cost of each system component is shown in Figure 6. This figure shows that the capital costs of the digester and biogas generator, batteries, PV generator, and converter represent 51.9%, 24.3%, 17.9%, and 5.9% respectively.

Table 8. Different configurations of the hybrid PV-BiogasG-Batteries

Configurations	PV (kW)	Biogas (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Converter (kW)	COE (\$/kWh)	NPC (\$)	Operating cost (\$/yr)	Initial capital (\$)	Fuel cost (\$/yr)
1	15	20	44	108	\$61,144	\$0.0473	\$3,858	\$26,126	0
2	15	20	42	112	\$61,220	\$0.0473	\$3,829	\$26,007	0
3	15	20	45	108	\$61,336	\$0.0475	\$3,865	\$26,256	0
4	15	20	44	110	\$61,384	\$0.0475	\$3,876	\$26,197	0
5	15	20	43	112	\$61,422	\$0.0474	\$3,887	\$26,137	0
6	15	20	46	108	\$61,524	\$0.0476	\$3,871	\$26,386	0

Figure 6. The cash flow by type of the optimal PV-BiogasG-Batteries system

Figure 7 shows that the biogas generator and batteries system continue to incur the total recurring annual maintenance cost of 6,763 \$. Further, analysis indicates that the biogas generator, batteries, and converter have the 20 years, 5.7 years, and the 20 years lifetime, respectively. This means that the batteries will be replaced at least twice during the lifetime of the project, according to the results obtained by Sanni *et al* [48]. In addition, Table 9 presents the annual electricity production for each component. It shows that electricity produced is 130,208 kWh/year for the biogas generator and 26,147 kWh/year for the PV generator. The annual energy produced for the renewable energy sources is 156,355 kWh/year.

Figure 8 shows that the total annual electricity generated is 156,355 kWh/year. In addition, it is clear that the electricity produced covers the load profile. Figure 9 depicts the demand evolution of the village over seven days (28-30 June and 1-4 July) in the presence of the 10.8 kW converter, 40 batteries. Table 10 shows that the biogas generator operates 8,719 h/year with fuel consumption of 397 tons/year, minimum electrical output of 10 kW electrical efficiency of 30.7% and produces 130,208 kWh/year.

Figure 7. Cash flows of the PV-BiogasG-Batteries system

Table 9. Annual electricity produced from the PV generator and the BiogasG

Component	Production (kWh/yr)	Percent (%)
Generic flat PV	26,147	16.7
Generic biogas genset	130,208	83.3
Total	156,355	100

Figure 8. Total annual electricity generated during the year

From the Table 11, it could be noted that the solar PV generator has a capacity factor of 19.9%, average output-power of 2.98 kW, the maximum output of 14.8 kW and produces 26,147 kWh/year. Table 12 presents that the unsatisfied load and the excess of the energy for this configuration are, respectively, 4,467 kWh/year and 11,296 kWh/year (2.81% and 7.22% of the total production). The percentage of unsatisfied load is a user-defined parameter, which in this case is assumed to be a maximum of 3%. Excess power has to be dumped into this system, which can be considered a negative factor. However, it also shows the ability of the system to meet future demand growth.

The battery lifetime and the maximum number of the batteries are 1.58 h and 44, respectively. In addition, the results show that the battery input and output energy are 6,831 kWh/year and the 5,470 kWh/year, respectively. In addition, the difference between battery input and output was due to the charge and discharge losses (1,367 kWh/year) and storage depletion (5.7 kWh/year). The expected battery lifetime is 5.76 years shown in Table 13. The output power of the inverter during this period is shown in Table 14. Table 14 shows that the converter operates 4,029 hours per year, with a capacity of 10.8 kW.

Figure 9. Demand evolution of the village over seven days

Table 10. Generic biogas genset (size-your-own) (biogas)

Quantity	Value	Units
Average of the production	130,208	kWh/yr
Minimum output	10.0	kW
Fuel consumption	397	tons/yr
Specific fuel consumption	2.13	kg/kWh
Fuel energy input	424,499	kWh/yr
Average of the electrical efficiency	30.7	%
Number of the operation hours	8,719	hrs/yr
Operational lifetime	20.1	yr
Factor of the capacity	74.3	%
Fixed generation cost	0.342	\$/hr
Marginal generation cost	0	\$/kWh

Table 11. Generic flat plate PV

Quantity	Value	Units
Minimum output	0	kW
Maximum output	14.8	kW
PV penetration	17.8	%
Hours of operation	4,379	hrs/yr
Levelized cost	0.0462	\$/kWh
Rated capacity	15.0	kW
Average output	2.98	kW
Average output	71.6	kWh/d
Factor of the capacity	19.9	%
Total production	26,147	kWh/yr

Table 12. Excess and unsatisfied electricity

Quantity	Value	Units
Excess of the energy	11,296	kWh/yr
Unmet load	4,467	kWh/yr
Capacity shortage	7,477	kWh/yr

Table 13. Battery properties

Quantity	Value	Units
Energy input	6,831	kWh/yr
Energy output	5,470	kWh/yr
Storage depletion	5.70	kWh/yr
Autonomy	1.58	hour
Storage wear cost	0.140	\$/kWh
Nominal capacity	44.0	kWh
Usable nominal capacity	26.4	kWh
Lifetime throughput	35,200	kWh
Expected lifetime	5.76	year
Losses	1,367	kWh/r

Table 14. System converter

Quantity	Value	Units
Hours of operation	4,029	hours/year
Energy output	20,306	kWh/year
Energy input	21,374	kWh/year
Losses	1,069	kWh/year
Capacity	10.8	kW
Average output	2.32	kW
Minimum output	0	kW
Maximum output	10.8	kW
Factor of the capacity	21.6	%
Average output	2.32	kW

4.2. Comparison of this study to others works

Table 15 presents a comparison of the hybrid renewable energy system for autonomous electricity demand. It shows that the hybrid PV-BiogasG-batteries system has lowest cost of the energy, while the hybrid PV-wind-battery system is most expensive. It could be observed in Table 4 that present study using HOMER Pro software is more advantageous in terms of energy cost (COE), net present cost (NPC) and fraction of renewable energy (100% which means no greenhouse gas emissions). However, during the summer season, the amount of the available substrate is lower, which directly affects the amount of the biogas produced and the electricity production.

Table 15. Hybrid PV-Wind-BiogasG-diesel generator from different studies in the world

Year	Country	Hybrid system	Software	COE (\$/kWh)	NPC (\$)	FR (%)	Ref
2022	Egypt	PV/wind/battery/DG	HOMER	0.157	533,654	78%	[1]
2022	Ghana	PV/biogas/battery	HOMER	0.256	506,629	100%	[20]
2016	Ethiopia	PV/biogas/biodiesel	HOMER	0.175	273,887	64%	[24]
2021	Pero	PV/wind/diesel	HOMER	0.478	227,335	94%	[29]
2020	Nigeria	PV/diesel/wind/battery	HOMER	0.106	1 million	77.4%	[31]
2015	Kenya	PV/wind/battery	HOMER	0.258	66,650	100%	[49]
2022	Mauritania	PV/biogas/battery	HOMER Pro [®]	0.0473	61,144	100%	Present study

4.3. Comparison of the hybrid solution to the national electricity grid

The Mauritanian electricity company (SOMELEC) charges 1\$ for every kWh of electrical energy sold or supplied to a consumer [50]. The price of a kWh of electrical energy sold by the diesel power plants (generators) that supply the city center is 1.3 \$/kWh. On the other hand, the proposed hybrid PV-BiogasG-Batteries system provides energy for 0.0473 \$/kWh. Currently, the government provides massive subsidies in the electricity sector in order to provide consumers with affordable electricity prices [51], [52]. The cost of the kWh produced by the proposed system is half of the SOMELEC's energy price [53], [54]. As the proposed hybrid system met the load demand with the lowest cost, the installation of this system will be the most efficient and advantageous.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to propose a novel approach for sizing and optimization of the hybrid solar PV-batteries-biogas generator based on the biogas resources. The developed technique was applied for the case of the Ain Farba in Tintane, located in the region of Hodh El Gharbi in Mauritania. In this study, we explored feasibility economic of an autonomous solar-biogas-battery hybrid system to electrify a rural area (El Medina village) that does not have access to electricity.

The study was done using the HOMER Pro[®] software, and the proposed solution provided very clean and emission-free electricity powered by renewable energy system. The optimal configuration was composed of a 20-kW biogas engine, a 15-kW photovoltaic generator, 44 batteries, and an inverter with a nominal capacity of 10 kW. Moreover, it had an initial capital of 26,126 \$, annual operating cost of 3,858 \$/year, NPC of 61,144 \$ and COE of 0.0473 \$/kWh. The annual electricity production was determined as 156,355 kWh/year, 83.3% was produced from biogas generator and 16.7% from photovoltaic system. Although the cost of the biogas fuel was assumed to be zero, according to the life cycle analysis. It was identified that the biogas generator and converter would need to be replaced once throughout the project and the battery would need to be replaced every 4.4 years. This has shown that the use of these electrical systems has great potential to meet the energy demands of existing and similar systems in the long run, thus ensuring the sustainability of the energy supply.

Developing countries experiencing severe power outages on the grid or African countries with many villages without access to electricity and producing a lot of animal waste which could be benefit for the autonomous electrification (solar supply and biogas) in these specialized facilities. The performance of the hybrid PV-solar, battery, and GB system is highly dependent on the actual further studies, to consider the components system health base on the diagnosis and identification of default. Also, the implementation of a system performance prediction model considering the influence of the climatic parameters variation and the characteristics of the system components makes it possible to better analyze the feasibility economic of the system.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bhatt, M. P. Sharma, and R. P. Saini, "Feasibility and sensitivity analysis of an off-grid micro hydro-photovoltaic-biomass and biogas-diesel-battery hybrid energy system for a remote area in Uttarakhand state, India," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 61, pp. 53–69, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.03.030.
- [2] K. Kaygusuz, "Energy for sustainable development: A case of developing countries," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 1116–1126, Feb. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2011.11.013.
- [3] B. K. Das, and Y. M. Al-Abdeli, "Optimisation of stand-alone hybrid CHP systems meeting electric and heating loads," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 153, pp. 391–408, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2017.09.078.
- [4] M. Goedecke, S. Therdtianwong, and S. H. Gheewala, "Life cycle cost analysis of alternative vehicles and fuels in Thailand," *Energy Policy*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 3236–3246, Jun. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2006.11.015.
- [5] G. Rohani, and M. Nour, "Techno-economical analysis of stand-alone hybrid renewable power system for Ras Musherib in United Arab Emirates," *Energy*, vol. 64, pp. 828–841, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2013.10.065.
- [6] "IRENA RRA Mauritania EN 2015.pdf." Accessed: Oct. 16, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/RRA/Country-Report/IRENA_RRA_Mauritania_EN_2015.pdf

- [7] S. Ashok, "Optimised model for community-based hybrid energy system," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 1155–1164, Jun. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2006.04.008.
- [8] N. K. Dia, A. A. Bayod-Rújula, N. Mamoudou, M. Diallo, C. S. Ethmane, and B. O. Bilal, "Energy context in Mauritania," *Energy Sources Part B Econ. Plan. Policy*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 182–190, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1080/15567249.2015.1010021.
- [9] M. Soukeyna, D. Ndiaye, S. M. Mustapha, and A. K. Mahmoud, "Neuron network prediction feed-forward wind speed network on Mauritania's North coast: Ballawack case," *Int. J. Innov. Technol. Explor. Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 2278–3075, 2020, doi: 10.35940/ijitee.K7853.1091220.
- [10] M. El Hacem Jed, R. Ihaddadene, N. Ihaddadene, C. Elb. Elhadji Sidi, and M. EL Bah, "Performance analysis of 954,809 kWp PV array of Sheikh Zayed solar power plant (Nouakchott, Mauritania)," *Renew. Energy Focus*, vol. 32, pp. 45–54, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ref.2019.11.002.
- [11] C. C. Ebeya *et al.*, "Influence of the construction materials properties of the biodigester on the biogas production and electricity generated by the slaughterhouse waste," *Int. J. Des. Nat. Ecodynamics*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 513–520, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.18280/ijdne.170404.
- [12] L. Kosnik, "The potential for small scale hydropower development in the US," *Energy Policy*, vol. 38, no. 10, pp. 5512–5519, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.04.049.
- [13] J. A. Eslemhoum, *et al.*, "Seasonal analyses of solar radiation on flat ground for different stat of sky: Case of Nouakchott, Mauritania," *Int. J. Phys. Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 125–138, 2019.
- [14] B. Bala, and S. A. Siddique, "Optimal design of a PV-diesel hybrid system for electrification of an isolated island—Sandwip in Bangladesh using genetic algorithm," *Energy Sustain. Dev.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 137–142, Sep. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.esd.2009.07.002.
- [15] M. J. Zimmer-Gembeck, and M. Helfand, "Ten years of longitudinal research on U.S. adolescent sexual behavior: Developmental correlates of sexual intercourse, and the importance of age, gender and ethnic background," *Dev. Rev.*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 153–224, Jun. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.dr.2007.06.001.
- [16] J. Ahmed, K. Harijan, P. Hameed Shaikh, and A. Ali Lashari, "Techno-economic feasibility analysis of an off-grid hybrid renewable energy system for rural electrification," *J. Electr. Electron. Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 7, 2021, doi: 10.11648/j.jee.20210901.12.
- [17] N. Ghorbani, A. Kasaeian, A. Toopshekan, L. Bahrami, and A. Maghami, "Optimizing a hybrid wind-PV-battery system using GA-PSO and MOPSO for reducing cost and increasing reliability," *Energy*, vol. 154, pp. 581–591, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.057.
- [18] F. Nawab *et al.*, "Solar-biogas microgrid: a strategy for the sustainable development of rural communities in Pakistan," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 18, p. 11124, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su141811124.
- [19] S. O. Oyedepo *et al.*, "Towards a sustainable electricity supply in Nigeria: The role of decentralized renewable energy system," *Eur. J. Sustain. Dev. Res.*, vol. 2, no. 4, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.20897/ejdsdr/3908.
- [20] F. Odoi-Yorke, S. Abaase, M. Zebilila, and L. Atepor, "Feasibility analysis of solar PV/biogas hybrid energy system for rural electrification in Ghana," *Cogent Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 2034376, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1080/23311916.2022.2034376.
- [21] A. K. Podder *et al.*, "Feasibility assessment of hybrid solar photovoltaic-biogas generator based charging station: a case of easy bike and auto rickshaw scenario in a developing nation," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 166, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su14010166.
- [22] C. Mokhtara, B. Negrou, N. Settou, B. Settou, and M. M. Samy, "Design optimization of off-grid hybrid renewable energy systems considering the effects of building energy performance and climate change: Case study of Algeria," *Energy*, vol. 219, p. 119605, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2020.119605.
- [23] K. Murugaperumal, and P. Ajay D Vimal Raj, "Feasibility design and techno-economic analysis of hybrid renewable energy system for rural electrification," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 188, pp. 1068–1083, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2019.07.008.
- [24] D. M. Teferra, "Grid comparison and feasibility study of an offgrid solar PV/biogas/biodiesel hybrid electric supply system," *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, vol. 7, no. 10, p. 8, 2016.
- [25] P. P. Kumar, and R. P. Saini, "Optimization of an off-grid integrated hybrid renewable energy system with different battery technologies for rural electrification in India," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 32, p. 101912, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2020.101912.
- [26] A. Baruah, M. Basu, and D. Amuley, "Modeling of an autonomous hybrid renewable energy system for electrification of a township: A case study for Sikkim, India," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 135, p. 110158, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2020.110158.
- [27] I. J. Mwakitalima, M. Rizwan, and N. Kumar, "Potential of a nonperennial tributary integrated with solar energy for rural electrification: a case study of Ikukwa Village in Tanzania," *Math. Probl. Eng.*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–37, May 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/1172050.
- [28] K. Y. Lau, and C. W. Tan, "Performance analysis of photovoltaic, hydrokinetic, and hybrid diesel systems for rural electrification in Malaysian Borneo," *Environ. Dev. Sustain.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 6279–6300, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10668-020-00872-1.
- [29] F. Rinaldi, F. Moghaddampoor, B. Najafi, and R. Marchesi, "Economic feasibility analysis and optimization of hybrid renewable energy systems for rural electrification in Peru," *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 731–748, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10098-020-01906-y.
- [30] A. S. Oladeji, M. F. Akorede, S. Aliyu, A. A. Mohammed, and A. W. Salami, "Simulation-based optimization of hybrid renewable energy system for off-grid rural electrification," *Int. J. Renew. Energy Dev.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 667–686, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.14710/ijred.2021.31316.
- [31] J. O. Oladigbolu, M. A. M. Ramli, and Y. A. Al-Turki, "Feasibility study and comparative analysis of hybrid renewable power system for off-grid rural electrification in a typical remote village located in Nigeria," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 171643–171663, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3024676.
- [32] O. D. T. Odou, R. Bhandari, and R. Adamou, "Hybrid off-grid renewable power system for sustainable rural electrification in Benin," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 145, pp. 1266–1279, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.06.032.
- [33] A. Eshetu Abaye, and R. Dengesu Haro, "Assessment of resource potential and feasibility study of standalone PV-wind-biogas hybrid system for rural electrification," in *2018 2nd International Conference on Electronics, Materials Engineering & Nano-Technology (IEMENTech)*, Kolkata, May 2018, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/IEMENTECH.2018.8465317.
- [34] B. F. Ronad, and S. H. Jangamshetti, "Optimal cost analysis of wind-solar hybrid system powered AC and DC irrigation pumps using HOMER," in *2015 International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA)*, Palermo, Italy, Nov. 2015, pp. 1038–1042. doi: 10.1109/ICRERA.2015.7418568.
- [35] S. Panigrahi, and B. K. Dubey, "A critical review on operating parameters and strategies to improve the biogas yield from anaerobic digestion of organic fraction of municipal solid waste," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 779–797, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.05.040.
- [36] M. M. Ali, M. Ndongo, B. Bilal, K. Yetilmesoy, I. Youm, and M. Bahramian, "Mapping of biogas production potential from livestock manures and slaughterhouse waste: A case study for African countries," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 256, p. 120499, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120499.

- [37] P. Abdeslahian, J. S. Lim, W. S. Ho, H. Hashim, and C. T. Lee, "Potential of biogas production from farm animal waste in Malaysia," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 60, pp. 714–723, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.117.
- [38] A. O. Avcioglu, and U. Türker, "Status and potential of biogas energy from animal wastes in Turkey," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1557–1561, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2011.11.006.
- [39] A. Perez Garcia, "Techno-economic feasibility study of a small-scale biogas plant for treating market waste in the city of El Alto," thesis, KTH School of Industrial Engineering and Management, Sweden, 2014.
- [40] S. O. Sanni, A. Awaisu, and T. S. Ajayi, "Optimal design and cost analysis of hybrid autonomous distributed generation system for a critical load," *Emit. Int. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 337–353, 2018, doi: 10.24003/emitter.v6i2.302.
- [41] T. Nacer, A. Hamidat, O. Nadjemi, and M. Bey, "Feasibility study of grid connected photovoltaic system in family farms for electricity generation in rural areas," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 96, pp. 305–318, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.04.093.
- [42] A. Aziz, M. Tajuddin, M. Adzman, M. Ramli, and S. Mekhilef, "Energy Management and optimization of a PV/diesel/battery hybrid energy system using a combined dispatch strategy," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 683, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11030683.
- [43] H. Z. Al Garni, A. Awasthi, and M. A. M. Ramli, "Optimal design and analysis of grid-connected photovoltaic under different tracking systems using HOMER," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 155, pp. 42–57, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2017.10.090.
- [44] E. Jedou *et al.*, "A cartographic approach coupled with optimized sizing and management of an on-grid hybrid PV-solar-battery-group based on the state of the sky: An african case study," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 227, pp. 101–115, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2021.08.079.
- [45] R. Fu, D. Feldman, and R. Margolis, "U.S. solar photovoltaic system cost benchmark: Q1 2018," *Renew. Energy*, p. 63, 2018, doi: 10.2172/1483475.
- [46] S. O. Sanni, J. Y. Oricha, T. O. Oyewole, and F. I. Bawonda, "Analysis of backup power supply for unreliable grid using hybrid solar PV/diesel/biogas system," *Energy*, vol. 227, p. 120506, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.120506.
- [47] F. H. Abanda, M. B. Manjia, K. E. Enongene, J. H. M. Tah, and C. Pettang, "A feasibility study of a residential photovoltaic system in Cameroon," *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.*, vol. 17, pp. 38–49, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.seta.2016.08.002.
- [48] S. O. Sanni, M. Ibrahim, I. Mahmud, T. O. Oyewole, and K. O. Olusuyi, "Potential of off-grid solar PV/biogas power generation system: Case study of Ado Ekiti slaughterhouse," *Int. J. Renew. Energy Res.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1309–18, 2019.
- [49] S. Ghaem Sigarchian, R. Paleta, A. Malmquist, and A. Pina, "Feasibility study of using a biogas engine as backup in a decentralized hybrid (PV/wind/battery) power generation system – Case study Kenya," *Energy*, vol. 90, pp. 1830–1841, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2015.07.008.
- [50] "Mauritania Tarifs Somelec en vigueur mis a jour (1).pdf." Accessed: Oct. 17, 2022. [Online]. Available: [https://rise.esmap.org/data/files/library/mauritania/Energy%20Access/Supporting%20Documentation/Mauritania_Tarifs%20Som elec_en_vigueur_mis_a_jour%20\(1\).pdf](https://rise.esmap.org/data/files/library/mauritania/Energy%20Access/Supporting%20Documentation/Mauritania_Tarifs%20Som elec_en_vigueur_mis_a_jour%20(1).pdf)
- [51] S. A. Memon, D. S. Upadhyay, and R. N. Patel, "Optimal configuration of solar and wind-based hybrid renewable energy system with and without energy storage including environmental and social criteria: A case study," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 44, p. 103446, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2021.103446.
- [52] Y. Alharthi, M. Siddiki, and G. Chaudhry, "Resource assessment and techno-economic analysis of a grid-connected solar PV-wind hybrid system for different locations in Saudi Arabia," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. 3690, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10103690.
- [53] M. Alam, and S. Bhattacharyya, "Decentralized renewable hybrid mini-grids for sustainable electrification of the off-grid coastal areas of Bangladesh," *Energies*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. 268, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.3390/en9040268.
- [54] N. Wamukonya, "African power sector reforms: some emerging lessons," *Energy Sustain. Dev.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 7–15, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0973-0826(08)60344-0.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Cheibany Cheikh Ebeya is a Ph.D. researcher at the Department of Physics, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya (UNA), in Nouakchott, Mauritania. His research interests are statistical thermodynamics, feasibility and modeling of a hybrid solar and biogas system, biomass and solar energy. He can be contacted by email: cheibanycheikh6@gmail.com.

Mohamed Mahmoud Ali is an associate professor in Physics Department, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya (UNA), in Nouakchott, Mauritania. He received his License Degree (2014) in fundamental physic. Then pursued a Master Degree (2016) in Applied Physics from University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya. He obtained his Ph.D. (2019) degrees in Renewable energy from University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya. His research interests are statistical thermodynamics, statistical mechanics, biogas plant, solar energy, kinetic modeling, linear/non-linear regression analysis-based modeling, artificial neural networks, experimental design, MATLAB-based programming. He can be contacted at email: med7md@gmail.com.

Mamoudou Ndongo is a professor in the Physics Department of the Faculty of Science and Technology (FST) of the University of Nouakchott Al Aasriya (UNA)-Mauritania. He holds a Habilitation to Direct Research (HDR) in 2015 at the Mohammadia School of Engineers, Mohamed V University, Rabat – Morocco and a Doctorate (Ph.D.) in 2000 at the University of Nice – France. His research focuses on the modeling of renewable energy resources and systems. He is co-author of about twenty articles published in peer-reviewed, indexed or impacted journals and of about ten communications in international congresses. He can be contacted at email: mndongo6@gmail.com.

Ahmed Sidibba is an assistance professor in exact sciences at the High Normal School ENS in Nouakchott, Mauritania. He received his Ph.D. degree in Renewable Energies and Electrical Systems from Gaston Berger University in Senegal in 2019. His research interests include the field of renewable energy and electrical systems. He can be contacted at email: sidibbaahmed@ens.mr.

Kaan Yetilmezsoy is a professor of Environmental Engineering Department, Faculty of Civil Engineering, at Yildiz Technical University, Davutpasa Campus, Esenler, Istanbul, Turkey. He received his B.Sc. degrees in both Environmental Engineering (1st rank graduate) and Civil Engineering (graduated as honor student) from Yildiz Technical University (2nd rank graduate), Istanbul/Turkey, in 2002 and 2004, respectively. He also obtained his M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in Environmental Engineering from Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul/Turkey, in 2004 and 2008, respectively. His research interests are mathematical modeling, linear/non-linear regression analysis-based modeling, artificial neural networks, fuzzy logic, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems, experimental design, multi-objective optimization techniques, MATLAB-based programming, scientific computation for engineers, design of water and wastewater treatment plants, fluid mechanics and hydraulics, and post-treatment technologies. He is 2018 TUBA-GEBIP member and has authored about 200 publications. He can be contacted at email: yetilmez@yildiz.edu.tr.

Emel Kiyan is an associate professor of Environmental Engineering Department, Faculty of Civil Engineering, at Yildiz Technical University, Davutpasa Campus, Esenler, Istanbul, Turkey. She received her B.Sc., M.Sc., and Ph.D. degrees in Environmental Engineering from Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul/Turkey, in 2002, 2004, and 2010, respectively. Her research areas are environmental modeling and optimization, post treatment technologies, genotoxicity, environmental microbiology. She can be contacted at email: ekocak@yildiz.edu.tr.

Boudy Bilal is an associate professor in Mechanical Engineering Department at the High Polytechnical School (ESP), in Nouakchott, Mauritania. He received his Ph.D. degree in Electrical Engineering from High Polytechnical School (ESP) of Cheikh Anta Diop University (UCAD) in Senegal in 2012. He is currently the Head of the Water, Energy and Sustainable Development Research Group in ESP of Nouakchott. His research interests include the field of renewable energy and electrical applications, artificial Intelligence, and intelligent control. He can be contacted at email: boudy.bilal@esp.mr.

Eslemhoum Jedou Abdi is a doctor researcher in Physics and Renewable Energy at the Physics Department, Faculty of Sciences and Technics, University of Nouakchott, Mauritania. She received her bachelor degree in electronics and automatism EEA (2011), Master degree in renewable energy (2014) and Ph.D. degree in Solar and wind Energy in 2022, respectively, all from The University of Nouakchott, Mauritania. Her research interest includes solar and wind energy in utilizing the artificial intelligence methods like neuron networks and genetic algorithms. She can be contacted at email: eslemhoum@gmail.com.

Halima Maiguizo-Diagne is a specialist in plant biotechnology and CAMES research at the Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research (ISRA). Graduated with a Ph.D. in 2017 at Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar after obtaining her master II in Morocco. Her research is focused on the recovery of organic materials using several processes including methanisation. She had to improve her training through several internationally renowned laboratories such as the LBE, the biotechnology laboratory of the University of Missouri-USA, the BIOMA of China. With international partners, she had published many articles, participated in congress meetings of European, African and Asian experts. She can be contacted at email: maiguizo@yahoo.com.

Issakha Youm is a professor of Condensed Matter Physics and Renewable Energy at the Physics Department, Faculty of Sciences and Techniques, University Cheikh Anta Diop of Dakar (UCAD), Senegal. He received his B.Sc. degree in Physical Sciences (1978), M. Sc. degree in Applied Physics (1979), M.Sc. degree and Ph.D. degree in Solar Energy in 1981 and 1983, respectively, all from Cheikh Anta DIOP University of Dakar (UCAD), Senegal. He also obtained a higher Doctor of Science (D.Sc.) degree in Solid State Physics from University Cheikh Anta DIOP of Dakar, Senegal in 1991. His research interests include thin film semiconductors and devices for photovoltaic applications, modeling and sizing optimization of hybrid systems, solar energy, and biomass energy (improved cookstove and biogas production). He has co-authored about 100 refereed publications in scientific journals and conferences proceedings. He can be contacted at email: issakha.youm@ucad.edu.sn.